

Kinetics and Mechanism of Bromine Oxidation of Formate

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The kinetics of bromine oxidation of formate has been investigated. The observed second order rate constant, k_{obs} remained constant with $p\text{H}$, ionic strength and substrate and oxidant concentrations but increased with a decrease in bromide concentration. Kinetic results conformed to the rate law $k_{\text{obs}}=k/[\text{Br}^-]$. Br_2 appears to be the only active oxidising species for free formate while HOBr has already been reported to be the only active oxidant for coordinated formate. A possible explanation has been given for such a difference in reactivity between free and coordinated formates. A possible mechanism has been suggested.

THE nature of active oxidant species in bromine oxidation was found to be dependent on the nature of the substrate. HOBr was reported to be the active oxidising species for mandelic acid¹, while Br_2 was established to be the active oxidising species for substituted mandelic acids², isobutyraldehyde³ and esters⁴. In a previous communication from this laboratory⁵, HOBr was established to be the active oxidant species for coordinated formate. In the present investigation kinetics of free formate oxidation has been studied with a view to decide the mechanism of the reaction and to examine the difference, if any, between the reactivities of free and coordinated formates.

Experimental

Sodium formate solution was standardised with standard potassium permanganate solution as mentioned in literature⁶. Sodium perchlorate and sodium bromide solutions were standardised by ion exchange method using Dowex 50 WX-8 cation exchange resin. The ionic strength was adjusted with sodium perchlorate and bromide concentration with sodium bromide solution. Sodium dihydrogen phosphate and disodium hydrogen phosphate solutions were used for $p\text{H}$ adjustments. All the chemicals were of reagent grade. A stoichiometry of one mole of oxidant to one mole of substrate was found by carrying out the reaction with 4 to 5 fold excess of bromine.

Kinetics of the reaction: The reaction was carried out in flasks painted black to avoid photocatalysis, if any. The course of the reaction was followed iodometrically. Under the present experimental conditions, iodine was found not to react with formate.

Results and Discussion

The reaction between formate ion and bromine was undertaken under second order conditions. The observed second order rate constants, k_{obs} and

their least squares deviation were computed with 1130 computer of Utkal University. The adherence of kinetic results to second order rate equation and the invariance of k_{obs} with either the substrate or the oxidant concentration (Table 2) indicated that the reaction was of perfect second order in nature. The reaction rate was found to be independent of the ionic strength (Table 1). The ionic strength was not, therefore, adjusted in subsequent runs.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

Temp. = $1.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$, $p\text{H} = 6.0$, $[\text{Formate}] = [\text{Bromine}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $[\text{Bromide}] = 0.3 M$

Ionic strength, M	0.41	0.50	0.60	0.70
$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10(M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$	2.69	2.44	2.63	2.56
	(± 0.12)	(± 0.09)	(± 0.19)	(± 0.13)

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF $[\text{FORMATE}]$ AND $[\text{BROMINE}]$ ON THE OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

Temp. = $1.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$, $p\text{H} = 6.0$, $[\text{Bromide}] = 0.30 M$,
Ionic strength : not adjusted

$[\text{Formate}] \times 10^3 (M)$	5.0	5.0	5.0	2.5	7.5
$[\text{Bromine}] \times 10^3 (M)$	2.5	7.5	10.0	5.0	5.0
$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10(M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$	2.95	2.11	2.69	2.10	2.94
	(± 0.14)	(± 0.09)	(± 0.11)	(± 0.15)	(± 0.10)

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF $p\text{H}$ ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

Temp. = $1 \pm 0.2^\circ$, $[\text{Bromine}] = [\text{Formate}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 $[\text{Br}^-] = 0.3 M$, Ionic strength : not adjusted

$p\text{H}$	5.7	6.0	6.3	6.7
$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10(M^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1})$	3.01	3.07	2.95	2.77
	(± 0.09)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.02)	(± 0.05)

Bromine in aqueous media in presence of bromide ion exists as Br_2 , Br_2^- and HOBr as per the following equilibria :

* For correspondence.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF $[Br^-]$ ON OBSERVED SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANT

$[Bromine] = [Formate] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $pH = 6.0$,
Ionic strength : not adjusted

	$1.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$				
$[Bromide], M$	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.30	0.50
$k_{obs}(M^{-1}sec^{-1})$	0.85 (± 0.04)	0.61 (± 0.31)	0.46 (± 0.03)	0.29 (± 0.06)	0.17 (± 0.08)
	$6.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$				
$[Bromide], M$	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.30	0.40
$k_{obs}(M^{-1}sec^{-1})$	4.13 (± 0.11)	2.74 (± 0.13)	2.44 (± 0.12)	1.44 (± 0.07)	1.13 (± 0.06)
	$11.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$				
$[Bromide], M$	0.20	0.35	0.45	0.60	0.80
$k_{obs}(M^{-1}sec^{-1})$	5.12 (± 0.44)	2.82 (± 0.06)	2.17 (± 0.06)	1.58 (± 0.08)	1.11 (± 0.03)

Calculation shows that under the pH range (5.7 to 6.7) maintained in the present investigation, the substrate exists as formate ion, $HCOO^-$ (pK_a of formic acid being 3.8). Under this pH range the rate of the reaction was found to be unchanged indicating that $HOBr$ was not the reactive species (equilibrium 2). Some experiments were performed at still lower pH (pH up to 4.4) using acetate-acetic acid buffer and the rate constant was found to be unchanged indicating that even if some formate ions were replaced by formic acid molecules $HCOOH$ (at lower pH) the rate of the reaction was unaffected.

K_2 has been reported⁷ to be of the order 10^{-8} at 25° . It follows, therefore, that

$$[HOBr] \ll [Br_2]_{total}$$

and hence equilibrium 2 is unimportant for the present reaction. Since the reaction rate was retarded by added bromide, Br_2 could not be the reactive species. It emerged, therefore, that molecular bromine, Br_2 was the active oxidant species. The kinetic results can be nicely explained by assuming the following reaction scheme :

From equation 3 it is possible to express the free bromine concentration, $[Br_2]_f$ in terms of total bromine concentration, $[Br_2]_T$ as under :

$$[Br_2]_f = [Br_2]_T / (1 + K_1 [Br^-]) \quad \dots (5)$$

The rate of the reaction is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_1 [Br_2]_f [HCOO^-] \\ &= \frac{k_1 [Br_2]_T [HCOO^-]}{1 + K_1 [Br^-]} \quad (\text{using equation 5}) \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, the second order rate constant, k_{obs} is given by

$$k_{obs} = k_1 / (1 + K_1 [Br^-]) \quad \dots (6)$$

The value of K_1 has been reported⁷ to be 17.8 at 25° . Since the present studies were made in the temperature range 1 to 11° , the tribromide formation constant, K_1 at the said temperature range was expected to be still higher. Under the bromide concentration employed, the following approximation, therefore, may be made :

$$1 + K_1 [Br^-] \approx K_1 [Br^-] \quad \dots (7)$$

Using relation 7, equation 6 then reduces to equation 8.

$$k_{obs} = k / [Br^-] \quad \dots (8)$$

(where $k_1 / K_1 = k$)

Equation 8 indicates that a plot of k_{obs} versus $1/[Br^-]$ should be linear passing through the origin. This was actually observed. The value of k was computed by the method of least squares using equation 8. The k values at different temperatures and the activation parameters (calculated from Eyring equation) alongwith their least squares deviation are presented in Table 5. The activation entropy is high positive indicating that a rigid transition complex is perhaps not formed. In our previous communication⁵ the kinetic results indicated that for coordinated formate [formate coor-

TABLE 5—RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Temp. ($^\circ C$)	$10 \times k(M^{-1}sec^{-1})$	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (k cal/mole)	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (e.u.)
1.0 ± 0.2	0.88		
6.0 ± 0.2	4.39	27.5 ± 1.4	39.0 ± 0.9
11.0 ± 0.2	9.65		

ordinated to a cobalt(III) centre] $HOBr$ was the active oxidant species and the high negative entropy of activation ($-\Delta S^\ddagger = 25.5 \pm 0.3$ e.u.) was ascribed to the formation of a transition complex. In spite of its low concentration, $HOBr$ acts as oxidant for coordinated formate probably due to its complex forming ability with the substrate in the transition state.

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